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Educational pathways of applicants for academic continuing education - The treasure within and its contribution to bridge the gap from "ECVET" to "ECTS"

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Abstract

The equal appreciation of vocational training and higher education leads to university admissions for professionals without classical academic educational qualifications. For this purpose the applicants have to go through a process of validation and formal recognition of their prior learnings. However, the format of this approach remains largely unclear; this is not surprising, as it is up to universities how the authorization procedures for these types of admissions are carried out. In this paper, the approach for the validation of the proficiency level 6 in EQF of the Danube University Krems forms the basis for the analysis of the previously acquired qualifications. We aim at providing an example for recognition and validation process of prior learnings, formal and non-formal gained through professional life in addition to educational qualifications.

Keywords

academic continuing education; permeability; validation and recognition of prior learnings

1 Introduction

Validation at the Danube University Krems, which has been strongly oriented towards European education policy (Orazbayeva, 2017), is identified as a process of validation of individual learning outcomes through measurement by an appropriate scale by an authorized institution and consists of the following phases: identification, documentation, evaluation and validation / certification (European Union 2012, p.5). Not only professionals with atypical educational biographies who apply for academic continuing education can benefit from this orientation, but also prospective students who have acquired foreign qualifications (Pfeffer & Skrivanek, 2013) as well as the equal recognition of non-formal and informal educational pathways of people with disabilities and chronic diseases. By means of individual validation, through the visualization of the competences equivalent to the Bachelor's degree, admission to the Master's program is enabled. This individual and resource-intensive way of admission to study then gives both sides, university and prospective student, clarity and security and it is delivered by written confirmation of the fulfillment of the study requirements for the respective course by the University (Kil 2016).

2 Research Context

2.1 Post-secondary and tertiary VET

Austria has a differentiated system of initial vocational education and training from upper secondary level up to tertiary education. Young people can choose whether to become apprentices in the so-called dual system or to attend a school of middle or higher vocational education. High school graduates can attend post-secondary professional education in the formal education system, where the professional qualifications obtained in secondary vocational colleges (Kollegs) can be obtained in less time and completed with a certificate that entitles them to work.

In addition, there are a number of non-formal training courses in which the required skills can be acquired for the pursuit of specific occupations, in particular in the field of health professions (healing massage, physiotherapy, occupational therapy, etc.). These courses very often require a high school leaving certificate, but are purely vocational training in the post-secondary area.

University education in Austria per se is not primarily designed for vocational training. It is true that not a few courses of study serve the preparation for the pursuit of academic professions in certain fields of activity (medicine, veterinary medicine, law, pedagogy, etc.), but the universities do not understand themselves as "training institutions" but as educational and research institutions that have a broader educational concept are committed (Gornik et al. 2018; Keser Aschenberger and Kil 2017).

Therefore, more than 20 years in Austria, the universities of applied sciences have been established, which offer vocational training at tertiary level (Pausits 2016). The spectrum ranges from technical, commercial, social and artistic occupations to health professions, administrative occupations and special education in the natural sciences.

Although there are no direct professional certificates associated with the completion of an FH degree program at the BA or MA level, graduates of universities of applied sciences almost without exception find a degree immediately after completing their studies, due to the study programs, which are very close to the needs of the industry Qualifications corresponding workplace. Not a few of these courses are offered to working people.

2.2 Further education in VET and permeability to tertiary education

For graduates in apprenticeship there is the possibility to do a professional master examination ("Meisterprüfung") who allows to open up a business as self-employed professional and to employ workers. This examination is not part of the formal educational system but is held either by the Chamber of Commerce or guilds. A similar exam for skilled workers in industrial companies opens the way to become an employed supervisor or foreman in industrial plants. Both exams do not offer entrance to the university system although in the Austria National Qualification Framework it is assigned on level 61. This is also the case for a number of non-formal qualifications both in technical and commercial professions like top-level accountants, auditors or management consultants.

The system of attribution of vocational qualifications to the NQF is currently under construction, but in the meantime there are references of classification in all competence levels which are relevant for the HE-System: 6, 7 and 8. A creditability of non-formal education

¹ Please see <https://www.qualifikationsregister.at/nqr-register/nqr-zuordnungen/>

even at higher levels for a study entitlement is currently not available in the Austrian system. It will be a huge challenge how equality is now handled in the individual universities and how individuals make use their possibilities to get access to academic vocational pathways.

In order to make vocational training, especially apprenticeship training, more attractive, several offers have been developed in the past to enable the transition to tertiary education. The most important of these is the "Berufsreifeprüfung", a type of baccalaureate that can be completed in parallel or consecutively to apprenticeship or training in a BMS. This exam consists of four parts: German, foreign language (mostly English), mathematics and a profession specific theoretical part. The preparatory courses for these exams are funded by the state. Participation in the courses increases steadily every year, but only a small part actually passes the exams. The completion of this exam gives access to universities and universities of applied sciences.

An alternative to regular apprenticeship training is the "apprenticeship with Matura". In this training, young people attend a high school and receive parallel apprenticeship training in a profession. This training lasts five years and ends with a double certification: a level A certificate and a final apprenticeship certificate. Graduates of this type of training can take up studies in tertiary educational institutions without further qualifications.

Without passing a "Berufsreifeprüfung" or a university entrance qualification (Studienberechtigungsprüfung), it is not possible for tertiary education graduates (e.g. apprenticeship graduates or middle school graduates) to take tertiary education, as there are no methods of crediting professional experience or non-formal education in the formal system of tertiary educational institutions acquired qualifications, except for Danube University Krems, university for continuing education, which offers academic expertise, certification and Master's degree programme for professionals regardless of their previous academic degrees. Next part describes the system of admission based on recognition and validation of prior learnings (formal, non-formal, and informal).

2.3 Danube University Krems

Admission to Danube University Krems is based on a systematic framework for the validation of non-formally and informally acquired competences which successfully passed the university audit in 2015. The validation of learning outcomes, in particular knowledge, skills and competences achieved non-formally and informally, plays an important role in increasing employability and mobility (see Wissensbilanz, 2016, p. 6). The Danube University Krems has developed a transparent and clear procedure and implemented quality-assurance procedures for this purpose. The process is supported by guidelines, instructions and templates for the candidates to maximize their previous experience and competencies in the application portfolio, as well as guidelines for tutorials, interview guidelines, process instructions, and training and coaching for the assessment process to be conducted by competent teaching persons.

The assessment procedure to determine admission competencies, i.e. to assess whether applicants fulfil the admission requirements defined by the curriculum (also known as enrolment procedure) is one part of the general admission procedure "The General Assessment Procedure for the Entire University" (AAV) is, in principle, applicable for all courses of study. This general assessment procedure has two differentiations (AAV-A and AAV-B), namely:

1. **AAV-A** to assess the admission competencies/acceptance requirements for Certified Programs (CP), Academic Programs (AE) and Master (first completed tertiary education) and

2. **AAV-B** to assess the admission competencies/acceptance requirements for Master (equivalent qualifications) if the applicants have not completed their first tertiary education (minimum Bachelor) (<https://www.donau-uni.ac.at/en/studium/zulassung/index.php>)

This study presents and discusses the access to academic continuing education at the university based on the theory and practice of recognition of non-formal and informally acquired competences of applicants with non-academic education. We want to visualize possible and actual paths to an academic continuing education degree through non-academic competences in addition to the formal qualifications. We will present the methodology clearly and preliminary results in order to discuss further evaluations and connections in biography research and teaching / learning planning for academic continuing education and the missing link between the vocational education and academic continuing education.

3 Methodology

This study utilized a mixed method approach in which qualitative data was coded and quantified and a randomized sampling method was used. A data base consisting of 300 student profiles was formed through innovative methods from the student registry of Danube University Krems. Application documents; CV in the Europass standards, letters of intent and work references were used to establish relevant biographical information and professional experience; their formal, non-formal and informal qualifications were recorded in an elaborate coding system and were quantified. Coding and data entry plan was drawn by the research institutes öibf and ibw (Dornmayer, et.al., 2017) which was approved by the university. For data protection reasons, coding was done directly in the study service center and in the department for quality management and teaching development.

This database shows the different educational pathways that precede the application at the Danube University Krems. For data analysis both quantitative (descriptive analysis) and qualitative (biographical analysis of students' all forms of qualifications) methods of data analysis were conducted. As a result of the data analysis, aspects of non-formal continuing education and informal learning were clearly identified, in addition to the formal qualifications.

3.1 Sample

For this study, Danube University Krems' student database was used. 300 persons were selected through random sampling. First, six subgroups were created according to applications to three faculties of the Danube University Krems - Health and Medicine; Economics and Globalization; Education, Arts and Architecture. Academic and non-academic prequalification was also kept as a distinct category in the sample selection. The sample was limited to applications for Master degrees and to time frame from winter semester 2014 to summer semester 2016. Within these subgroups, every 10th application was drawn. The students drawn were marked with a code to ensure anonymity and re-accessibility.

Characteristics and demographics of the sample were presented below:

Figure 4 Gender distribution of applicants by faculty

Figure 5 Gender distribution of applicants by academic status

Gender distribution is quite balanced in total, but there are differences regarding faculty and especially regarding academic background, 63% of the applicants without an academic background are male, while it is more balanced within the group of academics. In general 152 of the students had an academic degree, while 148 of them had no academic degree.

The average age in the sample is 37.6 years, the median is 36 years. Less than a quarter (23.7%) is between 20 and 29 years old and is therefore in the (broader) phase of "career entry". The largest group consists of 30- to 39-year-olds with 35.3% of the sample, i.e. people who normally have gained a foothold in working life and have established themselves.

Regarding the age distribution according to academic background, it is noticeable that in the first two age groups persons with academic education clearly outnumbered (28.9% of 20-29 year-olds versus 18.2% non-academic students). In the age groups 40-49 and 50+ non-academics predominate.

Figure 6 Age distribution of applicants by academic status

Figure 7 Types of first degrees of students

Average years of experience is 16 within the sample, while non-academic students have more experience (17.2 years) compared to students with an academic background (14.9 years).

Figure 8 Years of experience by academic background

4 Findings

Based on the sample described above, this paper examines the educational and professional trajectories of non-academic students and especially those who do not hold a Matura, and to follow their path to academic continuing education from VET systems.

A thorough analysis of the CVs and letters of intent indicated that there is a variety of educational and professional trajectories that lead non-academic “non-traditional” students to pursue a degree in academic continuing education. Following their biographical trajectories yielded horizontal and vertical permeability between their professional and educational life courses. Figure 6 indicates the trajectory of non-academic students who come from VET system.

Among all of the applicants without previous academic education at the time of application, 28.4% (29% of men and 27.3% of women) hold an apprenticeship or a technical school leaving certificate without the highest school leaving qualification. While more than 2/3 of them (69%, 81.5% of men and 46.7% of women) joined the workforce immediately afterwards, 28.6% completed further formal education, namely 11.9% (further) apprenticeship, 11.9% a (further) professional education and 4.8% a university entrance examination. Here, the proportion of women clearly dominates with 53.3% compared to 14.8% of men. The proportion of those who do not have any further education or training after the apprenticeship or technical college graduation is 9.5% as low and only affects men, which means 14.8% of the applicants with apprenticeship or technical college as a make up the highest level of initial education.

Almost 60% (66.7% of men and 46.7% of women) completed one or more further training(s) after entering employment: 14.3% attended a college or an academy, 7.1% completed a master's examination, and 4.8% made the Berufsreifeprüfung and another apprenticeship. Courses, seminars and trainings are not quantified here, as several courses, seminars or trainings were often attended by one person. 4.8% failed to complete the university degree or a course at a university they were enrolled.

Figure 9 Educational and professional trajectories of the non-academics after highest completed initial training: apprenticeship/ vocational schools

Looking at the individual level yields a trajectory of a person with apprenticeship background as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 10 Example of a professional and educational trajectory of a student with a VET background ("From the bakery to the medical technician")

The 57-year-old medical technician has completed an apprenticeship in bakery as an initial training, to which he joined a communications mechanics apprenticeship. After a period of professional experience, he completed a continuing education in information electronics programme to become a technician and at the same time, or overlapping, he completed a continuing education as a state-certified medical technician. In the subsequent professional activ-

ity followed by four further trainings in the health sector and in adult education and a degree in business psychology, two of which were not completed. In total, the applicant has 29 years of experience and 5 years of management experience. He has held his current position as a medical technician for more than ten years. The application at the Danube University Krems was for the study of Information Technologies in Health Care (MSc). In his application, his non-formal and work-based learning outcomes were recognized which lead him to a MSc degree without a Matura and a BA degree.

5 Conclusion

This paper is a qualitative work that delved into educational trajectories of the students who applied to an academic continuing education programme at Danube University Krems. Focus was on applicants with a VET background who do not hold a Matura. Results indicated that there is a variety of paths that may lead to academic continuing education at university level, through vertical and horizontal permeability; however, crucial point is the recognition and validation process at entry to academic continuing education.

Validation, recognition, credit transfer and qualification frameworks creates a permeable education system. Permeability can be defined as the possibility for “learners to be able to move easily between different types of education, (such as academic and vocational) and between different levels (such as upper secondary, or apprenticeship, up to higher education)” (CEDEFOP, 2012, p.1). It is underlined that “permeability must enable learners to transfer and build on all types of their prior learning – formal, non-formal or informal – wherever that learning took place, at school, work or even during leisure” (CEDEFOP, 2012, p.2). Permeability contributes significantly to social inclusion and accessibility of education. Danube University Krems is a very good example in this case as especially validating and recognising work-based learning and non-formal learning of applicants in a transparent way.

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Biographical notes

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Roland Löffler, MA. is project manager and authorized signatory of the board of the Austrian Institute for Research on Vocational Education in Vienna, Austria. The focus of his current research is on evaluation and impact analysis of labour market policy measures and qualification programs, quality assurance in professional (first) education (in particular apprenticeship training), skills profiles and skills development, and the development and implementation of monitoring projects on educational policy measures.